

Studies on the Interaction of Metal Ions and their Hydrrous Oxide Sols with Proteins. Part I. Interaction of Aluminium, Iron, and their Hydrrous Oxide Sols with Gelatin

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pH-metric titrations have been carried out to ascertain the binding of Al(III) and Fe(III) with the anionic gelatin. From the shift in the pH-titration curves of the metal and the alkali and those of the metal and gelatin, it is concluded that aluminium ions from the sol as well as from the electrolyte combine with the free carboxyl groups of the protein in the pH range 3-5. Viscometric studies, carried out under identical conditions, support the same view. Fe(III) does not exhibit tendency of binding with the gelatin. Chloride-ion binding with gelatin is also found to be insignificant.

The problem of the interaction of hydrophilic sols and hydrophobic colloidal systems is so complicated that it is seldom possible to explain the experimental data in a way as to incorporate the various factors involved therein. Considering the phenomenon from purely colloid-chemical viewpoint, attention might be drawn to the work of Pauli¹, who critically examined the colour variations during mutual flocculation of Congo blue and albumin sols and ascribed the changes due to conversion of NH_3^+ of the dye (blue) into NH_2 (red) during its reaction with the free carboxyl groups of the protein. Kvyat², on the basis of viscometric studies on the reaction of egg albumin, peptone, etc. with alumina and ferric oxide sol, concluded that the visualisation of some sort of chemical combination (probably complex-ion formation) between the metal and the protein was necessary in order to interpret the experimental results. Bull³ and Chatteraj and Bull⁴, on the other hand, had considered the problem from the purely physical point of view and had stressed the importance of the adsorption phenomenon during the mutual interaction of cationic protein on negatively charged glass. Since the whole problem of mutual interaction of the sols is quite an involved one, it was thought worthwhile to carry out a few studies on the interaction of metal ion and their hydrrous oxide sols with gelatin in order to have some insight into the mechanism of the process as seen from purely chemical viewpoint.

The present communication deals with the pH-metric and viscometric studies on the mutual interaction of alumina and ferric hydroxide sols with gelatin.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solutions of aluminium chloride and ferric chloride were prepared by dissolving A. R. samples of electrolytes in all-glass vessels in double distilled water. 2% Gelatin

1. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 723.
2. *Colloid J.*, U. S. S. R., 1939, 5, 449.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 190.
4. *Ibid.*, 1959, 81, 5128.

solution was obtained by adding 10 g. of powdered gelatin (Difco) in 500 ml of conductivity water; the mixture was heated on a water bath till whole of it went into solution. The pH of the solution was made 12.00 by addition of the requisite amount of caustic soda.

Colloidal solutions of alumina and ferric oxide could only be prepared in highly acidic range. Alumina sol (pH 1.7) and ferric oxide sol (pH 2.03) were prepared by the methods recommended by Weiser⁵ and Krecke⁶ respectively and were kept stored in pyrex conical flasks. The nature of charge on the sols was determined by means of Burton's type electrophoretic tube fitted with platinised foil type electrode. Both the sols were found to be positively charged. Since a comparative study of the binding of metal ions from sol and electrolyte was aimed at, the pH of the electrolyte solutions was brought to the same pH as those of the sols by adding a requisite amount of acid. The concentration of the salt solutions was 5.65 g./litre in each case. The respective concentrations of alumina and ferric oxide were found to be 6.6352 and 7.234 g./litre.

pH measurements were carried out by means of a Cambridge pH-meter (bench type) using glass electrodes (Cat. No. 42545 for pH range 9-14 and Cat. No. 42518 for pH range 1-9) in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode. Purified nitrogen was passed to create an inert atmosphere. The following sets were arranged and pH was measured after 24 hours.

Varying volumes, viz., 0, 1, 3, 8, 12, 18, 23, 26, 28, and 30 ml of aluminium chloride, alumina, and HCl, each of pH 1.7, were taken in 50 ml pyrex conical flasks. Two sets were arranged; to one 6 ml of gelatin (pH 12.00) and to the other 6 ml of NaOH of the same pH as that of gelatin were added. Total volume was made 36 ml. The results are recorded in Fig. 1. Precipitation did not take place when gelatin was treated with HCl or with $AlCl_3$ and sol below pH 5, whereas NaOH coagulated the alumina sol in each case.

FIG. 1

Varying volumes, viz., 0, 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, and 15 ml of ferric chloride, ferric oxide sol, and HCl, each of pH 2.03, were taken in 50 ml pyrex conical flasks. Two such

5. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1920, 24, 325.

6. *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1871, ii, 3, 286, 295.

sets were arranged and 5 ml of gelatin (pH 12.00) or NaOH (pH 12.00) was added as above making the total volume 20 ml in each case. The results are shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

Chloride-ion binding to gelatin was investigated under similar conditions using silver—silver chloride electrode in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode by means of H. Tinsley potentiometer, type 3387B. Some of the typical observations are recorded in Table I.

Viscometric measurements were carried out by modified Scarpa's method⁷, employing mixtures prepared under strictly identical conditions, given above, with the only exception that only those mixtures were used in which coagulation did not set in. The results in the form of a plot between the volume of sol and specific viscosity are depicted in Fig. 3.

DISCUSSION

Although evidence regarding the binding of metal ions by protein is available from the existing literature, very little has been said about such interactions in the case of their corresponding sols. The experimental results, shown in Table I, however, provide enough evidence in this direction. Considering the alumina sol (pH 1.7), probable combination between it and the gelatin would take place either through the counter ions (chloride ions), or the hydrogen and aluminium ions present in the inner part of the double layer. The fact that the chloride ions are negligibly bound with the protein (Table I) rules out the

7. *Gazzetta*, 1910, 40, 271; Frasad *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 1394.

possibility of any sort of interaction between the counter ions and the protein molecule. The only course left is the interaction of hydrogen or aluminium ions, or both, with the gelatin.

TABLE I

$$pCl^- = (E_{obs} + 0.0194)/0.058. \quad \text{Temp.} = 20^\circ.$$

Vol. added.	E.M.F. (volts).		pH.	(Cl ⁻) bound (moles/lit.).	Cl ⁻ -bound moles/ 10 ⁵ g. protein.
	With gelatin.	Without gelatin.			
	(a) Alumina sol.				
1 ml	0.1975	0.2512	11.43	24.86 × 10 ⁻⁵	7.40*
3	0.1835	0.2005	10.60	15.46	4.60*
8	0.1635	0.1695	9.29	14.69	4.40*
18	0.1390	0.1385	4.90	3.32	0.99
23	0.1308	0.1304	4.12	3.84	1.10
26	0.1230	0.1228	3.94	3.00	0.90
28	0.1120	0.1118	3.50	9.00	2.70
30	0.0960	0.0959	2.80	2.10	0.60
	(b) Aluminium chloride.				
18	0.1315	0.1610	4.24	5.10	1.50
23	0.1045	0.1042	3.78	7.00	2.10
26	0.1025	0.1022	3.70	7.00	2.10
28	0.1000	0.0998	3.68	8.40	2.50
30	0.0925	0.0923	2.40	9.00	2.70
	(c) Hydrochloric acid solution.				
18	0.1715	0.1714	11.32	2.60	0.78
23	0.1465	0.1460	11.29	2.90	0.88
26	0.1405	0.1402	10.99	2.10	0.60
28	0.1370	0.1364	10.90	5.00	1.50
30	0.1325	0.1320	10.00	5.70	1.71

*represents the chloride ions released during mutual coagulation of the two sols.

A comparison of the titration curves of hydrochloric acid solution (pH 1.7) with that of the alumina sol would reveal that the possibility of free hydrogen ion associated with the sol combining with gelatin is negligible in the pH range 3.7-5 because such an interaction would involve little or no change in the original pH of the protein (Fig. 1, curve C). A shift in pH from 11 to 4.8 can therefore be explained in terms of the aluminium ions from the inner part of the electrical double layer entering into combination with the protein. Possibility of such a change finds support in our experiments with aluminium chloride (pH 1.7). Further evidence to this effect is also available from the results on the titration of the sol with NaOH having the same pH as that of the gelatin. Here again, a marked shift in pH (although towards the higher pH range) is observed, thereby showing that the variations in pH may not be simply due to the interaction of the sol and hydroxyl ions but due to a definite combination of the metal ions from the sol (gelatin competes with its free hydroxyl ions in binding aluminium ion).

The existence of the flat portions of the hydrogen-ion titration curves for the sol as well as the corresponding electrolyte is rather significant. Since these lie in the pH range

3.7-5 (covering the region for the dissociation of the carboxyl groups from the aspartic and glutamic acid residues of gelatin, pK values for aspartic acid and glutamic acid being 3.4.7 and 4.7 respectively), it may be concluded that an interaction of the aluminium ions and carboxyl groups of the protein is quite probable. (Also it is in this pH range that the mixtures of the sol and gelatin do not coagulate, pointing towards some sort of chemical combination)⁸. The marked difference in the titration curves of alumina and gelatin, on the one hand, and that for alumina and alkali (same pH as that of the protein), on the other, cannot be solely ascribed to physical adsorption of gelatin on the surface of the colloidal particles, since gelatin below pH 4.7 (isoelectric point) would exhibit least tendency for such a behaviour on the surface of the positive alumina sol.

FIG. 3

On carrying out viscometric studies with these mixtures, it was found that a sharp point of inflection occurred with the mixtures containing about 10ml of alumina sol (Fig. 3). Since the point of inflection in the viscosity curve represents a new state of aggregation in the colloidal system, it may be concluded that it is due to the interaction of the sol and the gelatin. Factors, such as, the aggregation of the colloidal particles of alumina or the denaturation of the protein influencing viscosity variations, are no less important in such studies. Since increase in viscosity in the present investigation has been observed in the pH range 4.7-2.8, the influence of the factors mentioned above is highly improbable. In sufficiently acidic medium, formation of bigger particles of alumina due to coalescence or the denaturation of gelatin does not arise. All these facts tend to support that chemical factors are responsible for the existence of inflection points in the specific viscosity-concentration curve.

Unlike aluminium, iron shows a very feeble tendency of binding with gelatin since a small shift in pH is observed between the curves for sol-gelatin and HCl -gelatin. (Fig. 2). On the other hand, a marked shift is observed in the corresponding ferric chloride-gelatin curve giving the impression that ferric ions from the solution combine with gelatin. But that is not so can be very well seen from the proximity in the curve between ferric chloride-gelatin and that between $FeCl_3$ - $NaOH$ (the conclusion arrived at finds support from the fact that in the pH range below 2.5 most of the active sites of the protein are covered by the protons). In spite of the fact that studies with ferric oxide sol or ferric chloride do not provide definite proof for the combination of $Fe(III)$ with gelatin, the following interesting informations are worth mentioning

(i) A major part of the flat curve for the ferric oxide sol (pH 2.03) lies a little above that for HCl (pH 2.03) (Fig. 2, curves *a* and *c*), showing that more of hydrogen ions from the positively charged ferric oxide sol make themselves available for combination with gelatin than from hydrochloric acid solution alone.

(ii) Moreover, the variations in pH are mostly in the vicinity of pH 10.6 where free ϵ -amino groups of lysyl residues of gelatin are available for binding. The flat curve for ferric oxide sol, which almost exhibits a constancy of pH , shows that the possibility of the combination of $Fe(III)$ with ϵ -amino groups in gelatin cannot be ruled out.

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